

Luxembourg

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Luxembourg, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<https://eter-project.com/>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, three types of higher education in Luxembourg may be distinguished:

- Higher education provided by the University of Luxembourg: bachelor programmes, master programmes, doctoral studies and a range of other provisions, such as secondary school teacher training.
- Short-cycle provision (BTS programmes): vocational short-cycle programmes leading to an advanced vocational training certificate (BTS; brevet de technicien supérieur) currently proposed by a number of secondary schools (lycées). Programmes are accredited for a period of five years and have to correspond to the demand of the economy.
- Private and crossborder provisions: a series of private or foreign institutions have been accredited in order to provide higher education in Luxembourg. Some programmes are organised via crossborder partnerships, for example between foreign universities and Luxembourgish research institutes or professional chambers.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides an overview of the HEI types and some basic characteristics. Note that ETER data collection just covers the public University of Luxembourg for most data, the two private institutions awarding national diplomas (Lunex University and Luxembourg School of Business) are partially covered and classified as Private higher education institution and Business school respectively. The University of Luxembourg is the only PhD awarding institution in Luxembourg.

All HEIs in Luxembourg have been founded after millennium: the University of Luxembourg in 2003, the other two institutions both in 2014 (Lunex University and Luxembourg School of Business),

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/luxembourg/types-higher-education-institutions>

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Business school	École de commerce	1	0	1	0
Private higher education institution	Privat Héichschoul	1	0	1	0
University	Université	1	1	1	1
Total		3	1	2	1

Note: Most data in ETER only available for the University of Luxembourg

Students

For students, only data for the University of Luxembourg are available. In 2020 the university has 6,785 students enrolled, of which are 3,065 Bachelor- (ISCED 6), 2,768 Master-(ISCED 7) and 932 PhD students (ISCED 8). There are no long degree students enrolled.

Personnel

Also here, data are just available only for the University of Luxembourg. We can find a very steep hierarchy (see Figure 1), with just around 10% of the academic personnel being at intermediate or senior level respectively, while more than 80% comprises to junior level. There seems to be a considerable gender gap, in particular at senior level.

Figure 1. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Note: Only includes University of Luxembourg

Looking at the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners') (see Figure 2), we can find a remarkable increase from around 60% to 80% between 2011 and 2020, i.e. the already highly internationalized characteristic of the University of Luxembourg has even increased in the observed time period. This is on the one hand related to the smaller pool of local researchers, and on the other hand a strong sign of the attractiveness of the University of Luxembourg for foreign scholars.

Figure 2. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC), 2011 and 2020

Note: Only includes University of Luxembourg

Financial resources

Figure 3 illustrates the composition of financial resources of the University of Luxembourg. The majority of the funding (more than 75%) is provided by the core budget, followed by third-party funding. Student fees only play a very minor role.

Figure 3. Composition of resources, 2020

Note: Only includes University of Luxembourg

Changing roles over time

Figure 4 illustrates the number of students enrolled by universities between the observed time period 2011 and 2019. We can observe a rather stable development until 2016, but then a steep increase of nearly 20% from 2016 to 2017. The number of students slightly decreases again in 2018 but increases again in the most recent years (2019 and 2020).

Figure 4. Students enrolled at the University of Luxembourg, 2011-2020

Note: Only includes University of Luxembourg

As shown by Figure 5, with an increase of nearly 50% from 2011 to 2020, the number of academic personnel (FTE) at the University of Luxembourg is much higher in relation to the development of the number of students of the observed time period.

Figure 5. Academic personnel (FTE) by HEI type, 2011-20

Note: Only includes University of Luxembourg; data for 2012 and 2013 missing.

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